

MIMS 2.6.3//2.3.1//SS3.01

Technology as the 0th War Domain

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ABSTRACT

Technology is a subject which can in no way be ignored. Whether we discuss war, or scientific development, technology is a continual area of topic/concern. The author asserts in this paper that this (due to the MIMS aspect of war and technological progress) means that on a foundational level, technology can be considered the 0th domain of war. In fact, it remains prevalent in all the following domains, irrespective of our respect and/or grasp of it, mimsically speaking. On another philosophical level the author believes it becomes its own zeitgeist and gestalt due to its overarching importance. Examples given in the paper include computation, video games, martial arts techniques, missiles, hacking, jet fighters, and more. This paper can be a foundation for a more specific “technology in each domain” or produce a myriad of 0th Domain mimsical propositions, pre-engineering future weapons and tech to give decisive advantages in any other domain. This last statement is not particularly controversial, but rather than make the assumption, the reader should figure out why technology is so important.

Keywords: technology - military - war - application - computing - hacking - defense

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Note - You must use the Alien Language Decoder to translate the headings.¹

Table 1 - The P power applied to MIMS 2.6²

<i>Heaven</i>	<i>Mind</i>	<i>Discussion</i>	<i>Modes</i>	<i>War</i>	
<i>Man/Mind</i>	Polarity	Strategy	Orthodox	Conventional	<i>Yang</i>
<i>Earth</i>	Duality	Tactics	Unorthodox	Asymmetric	<i>Yin</i>

𐄂𐄃𐄄𐄅𐄆𐄇 // 𐄈𐄉𐄊𐄋

MIMS 2.3 and 2.6 belong to technology and strategy, respectively. In terms of the Strategy Series, we are on the 3rd iteration of discussion, with the 1st belonging to New Cold War³ topics, and the 2nd belonging to generalized discussions of Shi and strategy/stratagems. Topics retconned into the category, such as “The Art of Chess” etc. will belong to SS2.x.

With regard to the main domains of war, as defined in modern military text we typically see the following:

1. Land
2. Sea
3. Air
4. Space
5. Cyberspace

¹ <https://www.dcode.fr/alien-language>

² Please note the cross compliances with the 0 1 1 2 3 5 8 13

³ https://www.academia.edu/51022722/Winning_the_New_Cold_War_World_War_3

These are in the order of evolutionary development. In fact, though from refinement of etheric to more solid and from inferior to superior position they should be reordered:

Table 2 - The 5 Domains of War, reordered.

By Density of Terrain	By Position (Increasing Superiority of altitude)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Cyberspace 2. Space 3. Air 4. Sea 5. Land 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Land 2. Sea 3. Air 4. [Cyberspace] 5. Space

However, as identified in SPR 1.1, “Conquering the Solar System,”⁴ Part 3, Technology serves as the most vital MIMS for the procurement of the betterment of mankind. Technology and war (MIMS 2.8) have long been linked, since the earliest days⁵. From what can be discerned, true warfare began in the South American continent 7kya, probably as a result of the start of the Jovian era, midway in the transition from the Archaic to Megalithic Period⁶ as both the demonstrations of the Lord’s power⁷ (thunderbolt/vajra⁸) and of the tightening of resources due to climate change (particularly desertification)⁹, began to affect the governmental and tribal structures worldwide. In locations of highly mountainous regions (land domain¹⁰) and sea lanes (such as the Suez to Aegean Sea) we saw more rapid development.

J. Diamond¹¹ identified the correlation of high caloric grain foods as means to “fuel” the fires of war, but we see throughout Mesopotamia more than agricultural development but a whole array of technological advancements. So much so that between them, and the Tepe Period peoples, many (not only Plato) have speculated about a precursor “Atlantean” civilization which dominated land and sea. Meanwhile the Hindu maintain that also their pregnitors (and gods) even dominated the air domain in vimanas. The author dissents from this typical altstream explanation, however the factual existence of Mayan and Egyptian approximations of planes, and potentially helicopters and tanks is not unknown to him.

Currently the main domains of expansion and obsession for World War 3.0 are aerospace and cyberspace¹², especially the latter as it is cheap, fast moving, and provides extremely good leverage (per unit

⁴ https://www.academia.edu/62757621/Conquering_the_Solar_System

⁵ https://www.academia.edu/51641990/MIMS_2_7_8_War_and_Government_The_Rise_and_Fall_of_US_Military_Dominance_from_an_Art_of_War_perspective_and_MIMS_Analysis_as_well_as_a_short_discussion_of_the_history_of_failures_of_government_programs_from_antiquity_through_the_Great_Enlightenment

⁶ https://www.academia.edu/36753645/On_the_Origins_of_Religions

⁷ https://www.academia.edu/38268897/Sumo_Ancient_Ritual_to_the_Thunder_God

⁸ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332831733_Proposed_Discovery_of_Perattian_Thunderbolt_of_the_Gods_Strike_Location_in_Versailles_KY_Comparison_of_Predicted_Models_and_LiDAR_scans_of_Big_Sink_location_in_Woodford_County_Addendum_for_Plasmaglyph

⁹ https://www.academia.edu/37490311/Plasma_Petroglyphs_Plasmaglyphs_Earthworks_and_the_Megafauna_Extinction

¹⁰ https://www.academia.edu/40245389/Boxing_Out_Hyper_Masculinity

¹¹ “Guns, Germs, and Steel,” J. Diamond

¹² https://www.academia.edu/49950881/Asymmetric_Vulnerabilities_of_the_US_and_New_Capabilities_in_Geopolitical_Warfare_Including_Economic_Digital_Cyberspatial_and_Lawfare

cost). However, it is becoming increasingly obvious that one affects the other due to satellite infrastructure. The author has identified a SPACER¹³ strategy for economic expansion, and in SPR 1.0 “Birkeland Polyphase Superweb” also identified some weaponry. More was discussed in SS 1.2 “Asymmetric Vulnerabilities of the U.S.” and should be referred to therein, directly.

As for the effect of technology, the author is identifying 4 main spheres of influence for the “0th Domain”:

1. Leverage
2. Torque
3. Power
4. Potency

There may be sociological keys as well, discussed by the author elsewhere in classified texts discussing Access and Affluence, etc. However, in this paper he will aim to identify the main crux of technological MIMS, as well as the means to walk the fine line between “walking with a big stick” and “whacking oneself in the head” with it. It may require some references to martial arts or pugilistic, chess and strategy games, and other simulations of war. Actual battlefield examples may also become necessary.

Above all the author would like to emphasize the following three key points:

1. There is no denying that war funding has fueled technological development and may actually be a key biological principle in the *P* power¹⁴
2. Developing technology for martial purposes is tied to the cataclysmic past, and may be therefore also considered a spiritual or religious matter; the ethics and morality of which are in question. However what isn’t in question by any rational scholar is the presence of war and technology in religious history. The author asserts its the junction of these MIMS which excites rapid development in mankind, spiritual or material!
3. War technologies are not necessarily martial only in application. Many are medical, and in fact medicine itself - especially to the ancient peoples such as Han Chinese - were considered a form of the “art of war” (bingfa)¹⁵.

Therefore, with all of these points in mind, especially that technology was the main key to mankind’s development¹⁶ and rapid rise, let us examine it as the 0th domain, with some key examples and illustrations to drive home the point.¹⁷

The entire purpose of technology is to provide an improvement (usually through reduction of difficulty or the overcoming of some task) to human life. But, it may in fact be a part of the Universe’s function or modeling of reality, to include. Tools and weapons both are identified as the main subdomains of technology, and neither are exclusively human. For example, baboons use sticks to retrieve termites, and corvids are known to drop

¹³ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/spacers>

¹⁴ There is quite a lot of evidence of this in the biological Kingdoms!

¹⁵ In fact the word bing, here meaning “war” also is a translation for strike, and is used to describe disease.

¹⁶ Setting aside perhaps Organization, as a MIMS

¹⁷ Not that technology funding is in any danger of underfunding in our technocracy. However, the author has a bent that *certain* forms of futurised, under-understood or misunderstood technologies may be the key to martial victory in the NCW, WW3.0, WWII and space wars (alien or otherwise) to come.

turtles and other foods from heights to kill and open up hard shells. Obviously nature engrains various forms of weaponry into the biologically physio anatomy of many species. The obviousness of the need for these is illustrated in any discussion of predator-prey dynamics. However, it is far underscoring in predator versus predator situations.

For example, in one documentary/comparison video, two species of jumping spiders have an encounter¹⁸. They are approximately the same “weight class” and they do not “duke it out.” One decides to predate upon the other, and performs a complex reconnaissance using defilades and angles of superiority to attack. They are remarkably intelligent and have a certain degree of personality (for a spider). At the final attack, the more advanced spider with eyes upon the dorsal portion of the head, advances to the superior attack position above the less advanced spider. This is like watching a WW2 tank take on an older WW1 era tank. The maneuverability was only one aspect, and both had high levels. But the optical advantage was obvious. The upside down spider took the other spider by surprise, and was able to finish it off, and consume it. These two species were obviously in an arms race, and it would not be expected to be a long lasting race, geologically speaking. One will either force the other to evolve, or one will perish, unable to keep up with the demands of such a violent existence.

A similar, and very important video, was produced about the battle between Japanese giant hornets and honey bees.¹⁹ With Japanese honey bees, they have a defense against the battle-hard armor of the hornets: they ball up around the scouts and vibrate to generate heat, and this fries the scout’s nervous system (electrical), and kills them metabolically. However, European honey bees, which are prized for their honey production and docility, have no such defense. In one gruesome documentary, 30 giant hornets slaughter tens of thousands of European honey bees, ruthlessly. It is a strong lesson in the concept of not only air defense and technological detection (not that they could have stopped the scout if they detected it), but in the importance of having potent defenses and offensive weaponry.

Nature is replete with examples like this. Mother nature is the legless sea animal (sea lion) hunting the flightless bird locked on the shore, to eat it²⁰. It is brutal, and there’s nothing else to say about it. What defeats what is sometimes surprising. But underscoring almost every story is a story of technology. If the lizard outruns the snakes, it is the speed in the musculo-skeletal system, and if it is a polar bear killing a bull walrus, it is the tooth and claw, and just enough size, as well as the use of a chokepoint (strategy). Either way, the advanced tactical abilities (such as mantis shrimp vs. crabs, or bobbit worms vs. fish) are chances to see how technologies fare against one another, especially in tandem with stratagems. This information is built into nature, and in fact it was nature which influenced the development of Shaolin gongfu and early karate. Although, obviously, the main developments came from real human needs (like war or self-defense against highwaymen).

The truth of the matter is that the right tool, or weapon, determines the livelihood (ease, comfort... or downright survival) of almost every being on this planet, and probably others. Therefore the issue of technology is not only a matter of present MIMS and all types of mimsy (medicine, government, education, science, etc.)... but future MIMS as well. It could very well be that, more so than even the Scientific Method, technology itself (as it “bootstraps itself”) is the key MIMS for the bringing of future solutions to the present. Think about it, whenever great leaps forward are made, especially ones that excite mankind - airplanes, cars, computers, printing presses, etc. - they are always massive leaps in technological understanding and advances in both theory and invention/innovation!

¹⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=otk3f44fGDc> 6:30

¹⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-gAVlh-7WZM>

²⁰ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ldWA_bWSQHE

The author cannot think of five non-technological MIMS that have had quite the power of technology on mankind, save perhaps the fractional reserve system. And imagine the FRS working without computers! Even religion, and various religious revolutions (such as codes or rule of law, etc.) seem fairly tame in potency, and most of their power of shaping is owed or due to the fact of length of time of influence. Few technologies have the staying power of the pen/cil or paper, wheel, or chemistry. Most are constantly overturned. Whereas by contrast, philosophies and ideologies as MIMS tend to stay with us for eons. By contrast, prayer and meditation as MIMS are more or less the same, although there has been advancement in the latter. They do not tend towards the ability to constantly change and alter with time.

Technology, as a MIMS, is the fresh green shoot, and the tender bamboo root all at once. It gives and gives, and hope in it seems to spring eternal. That may, actually, be a problem. But for now, it is the paradigm of the day.

If deciphering this MIMS - the 0th Domain - were so simple, mankind would probably have better identified it as a study for the purposes of education. History, math, literature, grammar, linguistics, economics, sociology, politics, sciences, shop class... all of these have had very well defined (if not antiquated or politically volatile and influenced) curricula. But where has there ever been a defined course *on technology*? Only in specialized classes. Engineers, for their part, use technology and study its advancement as a matter of course. It is as if the self-explanatory nature of technology is such a given, that there isn't much need to define its power.

However, in terms of the martial sciences, this is not the case. Everything in the bingfa or arts of war, need to be defined²¹. A thorough review of the military academic journals and articles reveal an almost pedantic need for organization and definition. In fact, entire sciences have arisen - Operations Research²² in particular - from the engineering level precision needed to know the power of words. Only lawyers and surgeons seem to care more for the precision of words than colonels and generals.

Could words themselves be a MIMS and a hidden key? That seems to be one of the thought patterns emerging from this flow of the *Shi*²³. However, it is a not so hidden key, no?

Rather the author wants to focus upon the difficult translation (and here comes the mimsical application of this technical but martial discussion) of *Shen* - spirit.

There is a measure of a fighter's "keen", of an army's "blood lust", of a city's "ardour", of a nation's "resolve" which is termed by Sunzi (Sun Wu) as "spirit." It was said that the best general could ride up to the city wall, and by the vibration in the air, know whether it bodes well or ill to besiege it. In the author's boxing/pugilistic and tuishou (sticking hands) and grappling skills, that's precisely what it is. An internal gauging - a gut feeling or intuition - about an external and objective reality.

There is, therefore, a hidden technology here.

Let us utilize the tuishou²⁴ discussion, particular as relates to the advanced technical applications of Taijiquan (the "fist of the Grand Ultimate"²⁵). There are, so to speak, 8 major applicable techniques which are

²¹ In studying "martial methods" the text that should be obtained first is Sawyer's "7 Ancient Military Classics" <https://www.amazon.com/Seven-Military-Classics-Ancient-China-ebook/dp/B075S9NKPS>

²² <https://www.britannica.com/topic/operations-research>

²³ Where Shi denotes not the "strategic configuration of power" but flow and ebb, *propensity*. <https://www.amazon.com/Propensity-Things-Toward-History-Efficacy/dp/0942299957>

²⁴ Sticking hands

²⁵ This is a triple entendre, not the least of which is a referral to the thunderbolt or power of the Lord.

both the 101 and 401, as well as the master's level course, of Taijiquan, and which do appear in the top boxers and fighters' techniques (as well as in other cultures, like HEMA):

1. P'eng (ward off)²⁶ - referring to all acts of deflection, particularly by yielding
2. Lu (rollback) - specifically up and over one's Shi/position
3. Chi (press) - to create triangular pressure with rounded support
4. An (push) - to use force to move away
5. Ts'ai (pulldown/drain) - to drain and control with a downward pressure
6. Lieh (split) - to divide and conquer
7. Tsou (elbow/point) - to pierce and/or crush
8. K'ao (shoulder/bump) - to displace with a hard object or powerful weapon and force.²⁷

These "technologies" are identifiable on multiple dimensions, and in every war domain, through various techniques and stratagems. They are not exclusive to pugilism. Why? There is a timelessness of all classical knowledge which appears to come directly from the verifiability of objective, scientific, empirical, or logical knowledge related to the Universe's directions. How Causality works, in particular, seems to be both a) reliable and b) nonlinear. It is capable of producing repeated results, as in a chemistry experiment, or physics experiment, as well as unexpected results, such as outcomes of strange battles, like Thermapolæ. How is this? There is a calculation of the *N* power, beneath the core structures of the *P* powers and principles, which then alter the results of engagements and interactions.

Therefore, the Chinese, and others, identified forms or shapes (structures) which would generate repeated results despite the "jiggle" of chaos in the PPC²⁸. The entire purpose of any structure is to guide moving objects (a form of static dynamism) and generate power thereby (work performed over time).

So we must identify how it is that one can discern the vibratory status of any target, measure this, and then we can also easily identify a means for attacking that target's very vibration.

- A punch to the nose of a would be attacker currently talking and puffing themselves up
- A missile to the forward plane of a vanguard on its way to a bombing run
- An arc of electricity to scorch the surface of the intended recipient and blunt them (like arc discharge machining)
- A laser to the object to change is quantum state
- Any form of entangled data used to disrupt the quantum synchronicity in the opponent, to affect their "dæther"²⁹ and ability to coalesce energies, including gathering information/intel, or make plans that accord with the Changes of the Great Dao.

Bearing this hidden key, and the pinnacles of skill of the bingfa (according to Sunzi) in mind - disrupting the enemy's plans without fighting - let us then examine the *crux* of the use of technology as a MIMS in the 0th domain war fighting. How can we make sure that war is a MIMS and not an anti-MIMS... at least for ourselves, if not both parties... avoid destroying ourselves, and maintain our "virtue" (de) in accord with the Great Way? America has done this (twice or more, actually), but with both Vietnam and the lost "War on Terror" as well as probably the lost "war on drugs" it seems that we've done more harm to ourselves since 1950 than good. The

²⁶ "Tai Chi Classics" by Chan San Feng (pp. 27 of Weisun Liao's translation)

²⁷ One may be interested to note that another translation (by this author) for the next sentences may be "Advance, retreat, check right and left flanks, and defend the core area [the five phases]."

²⁸ Potentiality-Probability-Possibility-Cloud

²⁹ https://www.academia.edu/67236577/MIMS_2_102_In_pursuit_of_the_Daether

effects on the world, also, have been tremendous and in many cases very evil if not downright stupid and undermining of our general goals.

How can we use this excellent MIMS (technology) more responsibly, and achieve war objectives which make sense?

Figure 1 - Dao; credit: Bruce Lee³⁰

³⁰ <https://www.amazon.com/Tao-Jeet-Kune-Do-Expanded/dp/0897502027/>

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Leverage is defined, mechanically speaking, as force acting at a distance. The source of that force, however, is usually kinetic or a pressure gradient. Therefore, the question as posed above is really restatable in this way:

- How can we leverage technology to enhance our leverage (by applying forces at a distance), to achieve responsible supremacy (and therefore dominance) in a way which does not destroy ourselves?

It is important to note that the author here refers to the possible physics' principles which underlie all dimensions, including data and information, and certainly war and economics which might preclude prolonged force *if* that force drains the source of the energy (America, for example; or NATO).

So... what can be done?

Obviously, we need to refer back to SPR 2.0, specifically Part 3 where the discussion of computing power and Table 16 referring to computing types and speeds. The point made in the paper:

Computing power

Among all the MIMS, the one that the author **needs** to single out, which have helped mankind in the past to advance, to survive, to increase his/her positional advantage over a deadly nature, computing power has been one of the most faithful, predictable, and strong *return on investments* that has ever been done. In fact, at no time has there ever been expressed a lamentation for pollution or wastefulness for the computing power. People attack cryptocurrency because it is associated with finance and greed, but not because calculating math equations is the problem. From the abacus to the enigma machine⁵⁸², these MIMS not only advanced man, they often led the way well ahead. To this day we are not sure how the antikythera mechanism was invented. We also do not know how the Great Pyramid is better aligned to north⁵⁸³ than the Greenwich Mean Line⁵⁸⁴, prior to the invention of the sextant⁵⁸⁵ or astrolabe⁵⁸⁶!⁵⁸⁷

Therefore, the author feels confident in this statement:

- ★ The main key to humanity's progress is in the MIMS known as computing power "calculation", because the *N* power rests between the Aether and Physics, and controls the Force, but is controlled by the L power.⁵⁸⁸

⁵⁸¹ Ibid. "MIMS 1.0" pp. 18-20

⁵⁸² <https://brilliant.org/wiki/enigma-machine/>

⁵⁸³ <https://www.livescience.com/61799-great-pyramid-near-perfect-alignment.html>

⁵⁸⁴ <https://www.royalparks.org.uk/parks/greenwich-park/things-to-see-and-do/the-meridian-line>

⁵⁸⁵ 1731 AD <https://www.britannica.com/technology/sextant-instrument>

⁵⁸⁶ 220-150 BC <https://www.britannica.com/science/astrolabe-instrument>

⁵⁸⁷ Amillary sphere, Azafea, Torquetum, Antikythera mechanism, etc.

⁵⁸⁸ Or *C* power, if one is atheist and prefers to refer to Consciousness.

Figure 2 - Computing Power, the MIMS of calculation applied through technology; credit: author³¹

³¹ https://www.academia.edu/62757621/Conquering_the_Solar_System p. 142

Setting aside the need for [our country] to “get right with God/the Lord” (and win the frequency war mentioned in the last section), let’s focus specifically on a non-dætheral mechanism by which technology (computing power) will provide this leverage, without draining Source(s) - such as a Directed Energy Weapon would³².

It isn’t that computing power is not an arms race, it absolutely is. Currently, according to the [potentially propaganda] Chinese, they are winning. In terms of TIQ and all available IQ assets, they are definitely winning even if you combine the US with S. Korea and Japan. However, the author is not so sure that they are, in fact, winning that arms race.

But let’s suppose that they are. If they are winning, then we are driven to *catch up*. If we are driven to catch up, then we are actually boosted because computation is based on the *N* power, and as we are showing in the dæther work, already (with data) there is a provable connection between the two. Now, add in the fact that the computations are run with electrical devices (and this is not going to change, likely), you have a powerhouse of *F*, *A*, and *N* powers, all to leverage, or enhance our ability to utilize the *P* power, which itself may be described as **power itself**. There’s a reason the USA ® has so heavily invested in particle physics and various types of physics, and it wasn’t just because a bunch of Nazis joined the CIA after WWII. It is because physics and Natural Philosophæ itself confers all sorts of advantages over purely mystical thinking. We won’t review MIMS 2.2 here, as there is a superior paper in the works. Suffice it to say, mysticism without empiricism is worthless. Armchair philosophy, without data (*N* power) confers **zero advantage** and may, in fact, be an anti-MIMS. Certainly there is cause to wonder if Nikola Tesla was harmed by his shift from data backed NP to mysticism.

Okay, supposing now that we have one method of applying leverage - the use of computations to out maneuver and adjust the Shi (positional advantage) of the force-aligned fields of the PPPC in our favor. What else can be done? What other technological MIMS exist? Not to put too fine a point on it but computation is a slam dunk, anyone could have guessed that. Is there a way to literally apply a force at a distance? The author has already listed many new technologies in SPR 1.0 and 2.0 (especially Part 1), in particular the discussion of the Birkeland Polyphase Superweb:

- Orders of magnitude higher energy source
- Multi-phase power transfer
- Data exchange
- Potentially interacting with the Spheres of Heaven
- Controlling the Spheres of Earth
- Potential to move planets from orbits, or lesser bodies
- Modulation of the sun’s output, without kinetic interruption
- Potential to use the sun’s flicker for interstellar communications (“morse code”³³)

Might we control the “shen” by simply controlling the EM fields of Earth? Is that what HAARP does? Is the USA ® and China, Russia, etc. already involved in a complex form of asymmetric warfare? The author will leave it to the readers to determine their beliefs, after witnessing the events of COVID, post Wuhan Military Games / Event-201.

³² Either literally taking power, or harming Earth, or the technology being leaked and then used to attack [our country] producing a delayed Load on Source. Eg: nuclear arsenal.

³³ Not necessarily wise. This is Liu Cixin’s original idea, and a reference to his trilogy is warranted here as a warning in potential dangers inherent vis-a-vis “Dark Forest” theory.

The author doesn't presuppose to have all the technological mimsy at hand to predict. Also, some of the work/thought is classified, as it is too dangerous to discuss publicly. However, think in terms of AI, and deep fakes, and one will start to see how much of it connects back to computation, and therefore the N power, particularly data (dæthereal or not).

Φ ω × ρ π λ

Torque is more properly denoted as leverage on an angle, a twist if you will. It is applied angularly, and its presence felt asymmetrically. The best example, of course, is the way a transmission converts RPMs of a motor into the axles of an automobile.

Aside from mechanical technology, or even the Plasma Tesla Turbine™ the author "invented," how can we apply torque in a war or martial setting? The concept, the author thinks, is to utilize asymmetric motion, and "angles" of attack, which also apply directed energy, of various delivery modes, and act at quite a distance.

China appears to be going heavily into hypersonic ICBMS. But while these go "around" the world, act at angles, they are a linear form of attack.

Rather the author would recommend something more akin to utilizing the various electrical belts of the Earth to simulate and then generate arc discharge attacks over a wide range of areas.

Figure 3 - Torque as applied in asymmetric superweapon attack, probably instigated using targeted nuclear arsenal; credit: NASA

As for creating various forms of angular technology for war, the author suggests it's more a matter of applied pressure "from the side" or "from unexpected angles" than a literal circuitous path. Submarine warfare, espionage (via technology), and digitized lawfare³⁴ are excellent examples.

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What is power? Aside from the literals - work over time, and current x tension, etc. - we need to denote power from a classical martial perspective. Power is the ability to dominate or control in a domain or terrain with freedom, to alter the enemy, without oneself being controlled or harmed. It is a complex percentage, where no general (or almost none) is ever satisfied to have enough or convinced they have 100% control and power. That's *probably* true. But it may simply be an issue of logarithmic potency.

Regarding the application of power, in the use of technology - the 0th domain - what we see is that all technologies which give this ability are going to be a technology which is sought. However, as this is a very broad range, we need to talk about why so few technologies are adopted, and why so few are worthwhile of continual development (as say jet fighters, or aircraft carriers, SAMs, etc.)

The issue is that one can have all the power in the world, but if there is nowhere to deliver it, then what is the point? If one spends so much funding and budget on such devices, serially, quickly one will run out of funds and have little to no more power than at the start. Worse, each of these drains the source (military) as they then require all sorts of training to cover it. This may have already happened to the US military, it isn't clear how much diffusion and dispersion of resources has happened. But regardless, let us discuss the point of having power.

Having power only makes sense **if there is somewhere to apply it**. Having iron fists and massive muscles will mean nothing if the strike cannot land on the opponent. Similarly, high tech gadgets and rifles will mean nothing if there is no way to use them, or anyone trained in their use.

It is important to have the newest weaponry. But without a target, all weapons become paperweights and doorstops. Without a purpose, all technologies become fancily engineered philosophies.

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The other half, as mentioned, is potency. Deliver of power is about:

- Efficiency
- Efficacy
- Pragmatism
- Realism
- Repeatability
- Ethics
- Retaining defensibility
- Scalability

Think of the bookends of the American fight in World War II. At the start the American fleet was weak, and then mostly destroyed, with little ability to fight back. While America was a "sleeping giant" in fact it came quite lucky to not have the fuel tanks at Pearl Harbor blown up. No matter the technology of the times, which

³⁴ Foreign, programmed title fraud, for example. Or any of the various

was poor compared to Japan's naval fleet, but well ahead of the world's average, it's a cinch that because it was misapplied, America was doomed at the start. However, at the end of the war, America had the atomic bomb, and was also able to deliver that bomb with enough precision to let one be at ground level, and the next at air burst, and could compare the results. The second bomb was less lethal, but so devastating, Japan surrendered nearly the same day.

Potency is incredibly important from a martial perspective, and is talked about far too little. The truth is that most people are not capable of explaining it. Let us, again in terms of technology, and particularly with martiality in mind, define it.

Potency is the level of delivery of power, as measured by the efficacy and efficiency of the martiality (particularly lethality), and the penetration of this power beyond defenses. Systema is a martial art where, like iron body, they practice the absorption of power, even at a heavy dose of potency. However, the potency is blunted by the defense. One by absorption, one by invulnerability. In both cases, the tendency is to imagine increasing the delivery power, to overcome the defense. But, really it is an issue of penetration. For example a knife or bullet would easily overcome the defense in both of these cases. Similarly, there are many bunkers in the world, or super-tanks (like the M1A1 Abrams). But actually none of them could survive a projectile moving at 10% the speed of light. This puts the issue into perspective. Now are there punches that can overcome the two methods? Certainly. At some point the absorption technique would enable too much organ damage. And in the other, the rigidity would lead to skeletomuscular destruction.

Rather, isn't there a different approach? Yes, again to use technology (or martial technique in this case) to increase the penetrative depth of the assault. In the case of systema, and in iron body, one can use pressure points. Yilong - the famous gongfu iron body fighter - was defeated in just such a way, with a stray punch that connected with either stomach - 9 (vagus nerve) or small intestine - 17 (jaw corner), resulting in a stunning upset. In systema's case, an appropriate strike to the liver or spleen would easily defeat all absorption techniques.

Figures 4 & 5 - Yi Long (not a monk) absorbing blow after blow; but taken out by a quick exposure of neck points (gif); credit: YouTube

Similarly, if a technology is capable of penetrating defenses (for example hacking³⁵), it conveys a massive amount of potency. For this reason, the author recommends the US military, and common people, invest themselves in tools (mims) which confer massive amounts of potency, more than overwhelming power. Although, some such instances overlap (firearms for example).

³⁵ In fact, for this reason one of the asymmetric attacks the author most fears is scaled hacking. But that's a topic for a secret/top secret paper

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Video games simulating war are some of the most unique examples of mimsication of an anti-MIMS that I can think of. Of course, smartly, the world superpowers have taken advantage of the *positive* elements of video gaming to train and enhance troops and hand-eye coordination (important for drone flying, etc.). Obviously we all understand that the medical science and other things show some definitive negative side effects and main effects (sequelae overall) of video gaming and especially addiction and changes in neurochemistry in youth. The aforementioned 15 yo who inspired a paper is an example. He's intrepid and deep in thought, but he struggles with depression and reality. Some of that is age, some organ (zang fu) pattern (partially genetic), but there's a definite connection with excessive internet and gaming.

However, the author wants to focus not upon these topics but upon the act of simulation itself. There is a man - a controversial man - who passed on his knowledge of three business teachers, his name is Dan Peña³⁶. He presents a fairly excellent, simple but effective MIMS that is the foundation of all of his Quantum Leap Advantage reality, called "the Five Credos"³⁷:

1. Yesterday's dreams are tomorrow's reality.
2. Act with enthusiasm
3. Act as if you have no limits
4. See your dreams as if they are happening in reality today.
5. **Simulate before trying.**

This last one is obviously our focus, because we want to isolate the technology MIMS and war video game MIMS interaction. Can war video games make a more effective soldier? Some studies show that Olympic athletes and champions simulate and imagine victories before they happen. Famously Gen. Patton and Gen. MacArthur both fully believed and committed to their victories even at the heights of defeat. MacArthur famously said, "I shall return." He did.

What is the purpose, then of these simulations or imaginations, if not to enhance efficacy? And if that is done, then potency increases, then power, then leverage and torque, etc. Furthermore, as "Ender's Game" makes a plot device of it, if the individual is divorced from the initial consequence of their simulation made reality, they may do extraordinary things. Ender needed not know he was destroying the alien adversary, to do it.

Combining this with the mimsy of video gaming's embedded fantasy/sci-fi elements, and we see that, indeed, there is a strong likelihood that the war video game experience may create an enhanced war technology advantage. However, as war is an anti-MIMS, the author would caution policy and strategy decision makers that it very well could be a drain in other directions. For example video gaming itself could be draining, or war games, or war games about real war, or war games made into real war itself (and revealed to the individual), or maybe blinding would not even shield the soldier from some as-of-yet-unknown ethereal or dæthereal effect!

Nevertheless, it seems like one of the most likely technologies to continue to develop, and there is clearly a strong demand for it, and likely to remain one so long as mankind does not deal with the Mars-Venus holdover effects in myth, religion, sociology, etc. That won't happen so long as either the truth remains

³⁶ <https://www.danpena.co.uk/gla-library/>

³⁷ "Your First Hundred Million," D. Pena, 1999

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